

REACTIVITY AND WETTABILITY OF THERMALLY OXIDIZED AND UNOXIDIZED SiC PARTICULATES WITH ALUMINUM, AND ITS EFFECTS ON COMPOSITE FABRICATION

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ABSTRACT

The reactivity of unoxidized and thermally oxidized SiC particulates with Al has been investigated. The composites were fabricated by means of pressure infiltration. The particulates surface was characterized by several analytical techniques, and their oxidation was followed by means of weight gain techniques; the changes in the specific surface area were also measured. The extent of the reaction was determined by means of differential thermal analysis. The results for oxidized SiC indicate that once aluminum has reacted with the oxide to produce alumina, the direct reaction between aluminum and silicon carbide proceeds at a pace similar to that found for unoxidized SiC. The effect of the surface condition of the particulates on pressure infiltration of the liquid metal through packed powder compacts have also been investigated.

Keywords: aluminum alloys, silicon carbide, composites, reactivity, wettability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The reaction between aluminum alloys and SiC to form aluminum carbide [1-3], is one of the major problems in the fabrication of this type of composite [4,5]. Two methods are most widely used to prevent this reaction: i) increase the amount of silicon in the alloy, and, ii) utilize thermally oxidized SiC particles. The effectiveness of the second method relies upon the fact that the reaction product that is first produced when aluminum comes into contact with oxidized SiC is not aluminum carbide but alumina, a much less nocive and up to some extent inert compound (it should be noted that alumina reacts with aluminum alloys that contain magnesium,

see for example ref. [1,6]).

In a previous publication we presented an extensive study of reactivity between Al-Si alloys and thermally oxidized and unoxidized SiC particulates [7]. The surface condition of the particles was also studied in detail. The present paper is mainly addressed to investigate the correlation between reactivity and wettability at the aluminum/SiC interface. Some of the previous results [7] will be first summarized. Then the effects of several heat treatments of the SiC particles on pressure infiltration [8,9] of packed samples of SiC particulates by pure Al, will be discussed.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The composites were fabricated by means of pressure infiltration in an experimental set up that has been described elsewhere [8,9]. To keep the extent of the reaction during the fabrication process at a low level, the following conditions were used: a) an applied pressure well above threshold [8,9], b) a short infiltration time (15 s), and, c) a moderate temperature (700 °C). The investigation of wettability at the Al-SiC particulates interface was carried out by means of the same apparatus and following the procedures discussed in ref. [9]. For instance in this case the infiltrations were done at 700 °C and for 120 s. The threshold pressure was determined by measuring the infiltrated height as a function of the applied pressure.

Pure aluminum (99.98 wt%) was melted in an alumina crucible. The liquid metal was degassed and cleaned by bubbling an inert gas (argon). Three commercial SiC particulates from different suppliers (A, B and C of Table I) were used. The particulates were packed into quartz tubes by alternating strokes of a weight and vibrations. The resultant particle volume fraction (V_p) is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Some characteristics of the SiC particulates used in this work: V_p stands for particle volume fraction, D is the average particle diameter, and P_0 is the threshold pressure for the particulates in the as-received condition. The threshold pressure for particulates C oxidized at 1000 °C for 18 h, is also reported (in parenthesis).

Code	Type	Purity	$D(\mu\text{m})$	V_p	P_0 (kPa)
A	black	99.0%	44	0.56	460
B	black	98.7%	51	0.59	405
C	green	99.5%	27	0.59	570 (490)

The characterization of the particulates was carried out by means of Fourier Transform Infrared Absorption spectroscopy (FTIR) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The infrared spectra were recorded in a Perkin Elmer FTIR 1725 X apparatus (the particulates were set in KBr

wafers). The SiC particulates were used as-received and after heat treatments at temperatures up to 1000°C. The weight loss that precedes oxidation, originated by the burning of organic residues [7], was followed by means of thermogravimetry. A Perkin Elmer TGA 7 Thermogravimetric Analyzer was used in these measurements. The degree of oxidation was determined by measuring the increase in weight. The effects of oxidation on the surface roughness were examined by means of adsorption isotherms. The adsorption isotherms of N₂ at -196 °C were determined in an Omnisorp-100 Analyzer which covers the pressure range of 10⁻⁷-1.0 atm. In all cases, samples of SiC dried at 110 °C were outgassed in situ (300 °C) for 12 h under high vacuum, to ensure thorough cleaning of the SiC surface prior to the adsorption measurements.

The extent of the reaction between aluminum and the SiC particles was followed by means of optical microscopy and quantified in the way suggested in ref. [10]. The latter method consists in measuring the changes in the liquidus temperature of the alloy (see below). The present measurements were carried out in a Perkin Elmer DTA 1700 Differential Thermal Analyzer, under a dynamic argon atmosphere (1 l h⁻¹) at a heating rate of 10°C min⁻¹. Pure alumina was used as reference. The heat treatments of the composites were done in the same DTA apparatus, using a heating rate, up to the chosen temperature, of 80°C min⁻¹.

3. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE PARTICULATES

3.1 Characterization of the particulates

The FTIR spectra (Fig. 1) indicate that particulates A have more hydroxyl radicals (peak at 3600 cm⁻¹) and aliphatic hydrocarbons (2800 cm⁻¹) than particulates B and C (the spectrum of particulates C is similar to that of B). They also reveal the presence of carbonates (1400 cm⁻¹) in A, which are absent in B and C. Furthermore, the degree of oxidation (the wavenumber of the vibration of the SiO₂ bond lies at 1080-1100 cm⁻¹) is higher in A than in B. The last peak at 900 cm⁻¹ corresponds to SiC. These results agree with SEM images that reveal a larger amount of residues in particulates A.

3.2 Oxidation of SiC particulates

The increase in weight of particulates B along the oxidation heat treatment at 1000°C is shown in Fig. 2. The results indicate that oxidation proceeds at a very high pace up to 25 h at temperature. Beyond this point the oxidation rate is very small, although finite, up to the maximum time at temperature explored in this work. Heat treatments at lower temperatures appreciably reduce the weight of particulates A, as shown in Fig. 3. This is due to the burning of the organic residues that were detected by FTIR. This weight loss is much less important in

particulates B and C, in agreement with the FTIR results.

The adsorption isotherms revealed that oxidation strongly reduces the surface roughness of the particulates. For instance the specific surface area of particulates B decreases from $0.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (unoxidized) to $0.05 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (100h at temperature). It is interesting to note that the latter result nearly coincides with the result given by the technique that was used to determine the average particle size (laser light scattering), namely, $0.046 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. This indicates that oxidized particulates have a rather flat surface.

Figure 1. Infrared Absorption spectra of particulates A (a) and B (b) of Table I. (c) corresponds to particulates B after 100 h at 1000°C .

The FTIR spectra for the oxidized particulates, as compared to those of unoxidized particulates (curves b and c in Fig. 1), show the following features: a) a strong reduction of the peaks in the region $3600\text{--}2800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, revealing an important decrease in water and organic matter at the surface of the particulates, b) an enhancement of the peak associated to SiO_2 ($1080\text{--}1100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Figure 2. Weight gain of particulates B subjected to an oxidation heat treatment at 1000°C , as a function of time at temperature.

Figure 3. Weight loss in particulates A of Table I as a function of temperature, as determined by means of thermogravimetry (heating rate 20 K min^{-1}).

4. REACTIVITY OF SiC PARTICULATES WITH ALUMINUM

4.1 Reactions of oxidized and unoxidized SiC with aluminium

Liquid(l) aluminum reacts with solid(s) SiC through the following reaction

This reaction is unfavorable as it stands, and only occurs in the presence of bulk liquid aluminum. In the latter case the dissolution of free silicon in liquid aluminum decreases the free energy, which can eventually become negative. The critical concentration of silicon, that is the one below which reaction (1) occurs, can be obtained from its associated free energy [7]. Our results indicate that a rather large amount of silicon in the alloy is required to block the reaction, for instance at 700°C the critical concentration is around 23 wt% of silicon.

When the particulates are oxidized, the first reaction that takes place, once they get in contact with liquid aluminum, is

This reaction is very exothermic and, contrary to reaction (1), it is favorable even if the dissolution of the resulting silicon in liquid aluminum is not taken into account. A relevant question is how reaction (1) proceeds once the silicon dioxide at the surface of the particulates has been consumed, this is considered in the next subsection. Finally it is interesting to note that the two reactions produce the same amount of free Si.

4.2 Extent of the reaction: DTA results

As already mentioned, we have evaluated the extent of reactions (1) and (3) by means of DTA [10]. The dissolution of the free silicon produced in these reactions, in the alloy forming part of the composite, decreases its liquidus temperature; these changes can be easily determined by DTA. The results for the composites containing oxidized and unoxidized SiC particulates are shown in Fig. 4. The composites were heat treated at different temperatures for 30 min. The increase of the silicon content of the alloy in the as-cast condition or after heat treatment at low temperature (below the melting point) increases with the degree of oxidation of the particulates. This is a consequence of the very high reactivity between aluminum and silicon oxide, as discussed in the previous subsection. The results do also indicate that once the oxide layer has

been consumed, the direct reaction between aluminum and silicon carbide proceeds at a pace similar to that found for unoxidized SiC.

Optical microscopy showed that, as expected, the amount of aluminum carbide produced in the reaction is less in the case of oxidized particulates. Its morphology also changes, appearing in the form of large particles in the case of unoxidized SiC, and as rather uniform layers at the surface of the particulates or much smaller particles, in the case of oxidized SiC. Furthermore, in the latter case it appears restricted to regions near the particulates, whereas in the case of unoxidized particulates its spatial distribution is more uniform.

Figure 4. Changes in the silicon content in the metal forming part of composite. Circles: unoxidized SiC. Squares and triangles: oxidized SiC at 1000 °C for 18 h and 100 h respectively.

5. EFFECTS OF HEAT TREATMENT OF THE SiC PARTICULATES ON WETTABILITY

During fabrication of the composites, it was observed that whereas those containing particulates B and C were very homogeneous and with a very low porosity, in those of particulates A infiltration was rather limited. In the latter the metal penetrated through channels instead of filling the whole sample. This is likely due to the larger amount of organic residues observed in particulates A. To quantify this result, we measured the infiltration height (h) as a function of applied pressure (P) for particulates A before and after a heat treatment at 600 °C for 30 min (this temperature was chosen by analyzing the results of Fig. 3). The results of Fig. 5 show that this heat treatment almost eliminate the large dispersion of the results obtained for untreated particulates. This illustrates how heat treatment at low temperatures changes the intrinsic permeability of packed samples of SiC particulates. On the other hand, oxidation at higher temperatures appreciably decreases the threshold pressure, as indicated by the results reported in Fig. 6 and Table 1. This decrease can be either due to the direct reaction between aluminum and SiC (difficulted by the oxide film that covers the surface of the liquid metal) or to the changes in the specific surface area promoted by oxidation, or to both. A more detailed analysis is required to clarify these questions.

Figure 5. Infiltrated height as a function of applied pressure for pure aluminum and SiC particulates A of Table I.

Figure 6. Infiltrated height as a function of applied pressure for pure aluminum and particulates C of Table I, without heat treatment and oxidized at 1000 °C for 18 h.

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